

VOCABULARY OF THE LANGUAGE WITHOUT ALTERNATIVE LEXICON AND ITS LINGUISTIC AND EXTRA LINGUISTIC FOUNDATIONS

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Abstract: This article will be devoted to the study of non-alternative lexicons in the vocabulary structure of the language. Linguistic and extra linguistic grounds are also considered and discussed.

Keywords: linguistics, non-alternative lexicon, language, translation, native vocabulary.

Introduction

In any language or dialect, there will be words that cannot be translated into another language in one word. Such words are called an alternative-free lexicon. An alternative lexicon reflects situational or conditional characteristic of a particular folk culture. It is often associated with money, distance-units of length, household items, clothing, food-drink, etc. or characteristic of the local people, like it is composed of words that mean concepts. When an alternative lexicon is assimilated into another language, they are called exotic lexicons (exotisms). Exotisms and ethnografisms are considered symbols of a different culture. Including Speaker, cricket, Schilling-England; pasture, village, ditch, peasant, desert

- Central Asia; sakura, Geisha, Ikebana, sake - associate signs of Japanese culture. Signs of Uzbek culture include pilaf, patir, sumalak, bat, belt (there is a belt at the waist), skullcap (the skullcap is in the sky, the skullcap is narrow), etc. can be given as an example in words.

Translating a lexicon into another language without an alternative does not denote the actual meaning itself. Therefore, it is advisable to interpret it by transliteration.

MAIN PART

The interpretation of the "dollar" of the United States, the English "pound sterling", the German "marka", Indian "rupee", the Afghan "Afghani" without transliteration, the Uzbek "sum", the US "brand", the English "whiskey", the Russian "vodka" of the German "schnapsee", the Uzbek wearing "duppi" instead of the "hat" on the head in English, wearing "tun" or "yaktak" in Uzbek instead of wearing "coat" in English has the same meaning.

When a word in one language cannot be translated to an alternative in another language, the phenomenon of Lacuna happens. The lagoons (lat. lacuna - space,

depth, chamois) - the place where the text is empty, falling, is "white spots on the semantic map of the language." Like the alternative lexicon, lacunae are felt in the analogy of languages. For example, attorney "representative", who represents the diversity of the profession of lawyer other than the English word lawyer, which means "lawyer, lawyer", barrister "lawyer who has the right to participate in the Supreme Courts", solicitor "who advises clients and organizations; has the right to participate in the lower courts", counseryurisconsult", counsellor "consultant", advocate "lawyer of the highest level" (Great Britain, 1978). Only one lawyer will be an alternative to the expressions recorded in Uzbek and Russian.

Mythologized Language units. These are archetypes and mythologies, narratives, eateries and traditions. In each specific phrase, not a whole-headed myth is reflected, but a mythology. A mythology is the "main character" of a myth, it can be an important character or condition, and it can go from myth to myth. On the basis of the myth usually lies the archetype. Archetype is a stable image that appears in the minds of individuals and spreads in culture. The concept of archetype K.G. introduced into circulation in the article "instinct of unconsciousness", published by Jung in 1919. K. G. According to Jung, all people will have an innate ability to inanimate archetypes - some common symbols that appear in dreams, myths, fairy tales and legends. Archetypes express "collective inhumanity" inherited from ancestors, and not as a result of personal experience. K. Jung defines within the framework of genetic theory that the archetype is closely related to mythology. Consequently, mythology is a storehouse of archetypes.

In the Uzbek daily life, bread is an important feed. Our people respect bread for a long time, know it above all, dear and holy. Traditions, left by the ancestors, according to tradition, does not even bite the bread upside down, does not put other things on top of the bread, does not overstep the bread, if the bread falls from hand to ground, they immediately take it, kiss it three times, push it to their foreheads, if they see the bread crumb on the table, they wet Respectfully treating bread is taught to children from an early age, they are taught the need to collect the bread's grip from the ground, honor it and not trample it. When an Uzbek sets out, he will certainly take bread with him. Accordingly, on the basis of phrases such as non yemok, noni butun, noni yarimta bolmoq, non ursin, in the composition of which the bread component was involved, the bread archetype comes as a symbol of life, livelihood, sustenance, fullness. The bread archetype, consequently, is that the bread is found with the skin of the forehead, that it is eaten honestly, starting with the sacred books ("you are taken from the Earth, and

you will eat bread with the skin of the forehead until you return to Earth." Genesis3. 620p.) , in Uzbek folk epics, fairy tales, legends, etc. are authenticated.

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